

TURLI CHEGARALANISHLI HOL UCHUN Π STRATEGIYANING QURILISHI HAQIDA

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Annotasiya: Ushbu maqolada Π strategiyaning geometrik chegaralanish, integro – geometrik chegaralanishli holatlar uchun qurilishi yoritilgan. Π strategiyaning qurilishi turli chegaralanishli hol uchun quvish – qochish maslasining yechimlariga uzviy bog‘liqligi isbotlangan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Π strategiya, geometrik chegaralanish, integro – geometrik chegaralanish.

О ПОСТРОЕНИИ Π – СТАТЕГИИИ ДЛЯ РАЗЛИЧНЫХ ГРАНИЧНЫХ СЛУЧАЕВ

Аннотация: В статье описано построение Π стратегии для геометрически ограниченных, интегро-геометрически ограниченных случаев. Доказано, что построение Π -стратегии неразрывно связано с решением задачи погони-убегания для различных предельных случаев.

Ключевые слова: Π стратегии, геометрическое ограничение, интегро - геометрическое ограничение

ON THE CONSTRUCTION OF Π STRATEGY FOR DIFFERENT BOUNDARY CASES

Annotation: This article describes the construction of strategy P for geometric bounded, integro-geometrically bounded cases. It has been proved that the

construction of P strategy is inextricably linked to the solutions of the chase-escape problem for different limiting cases.

Keywords: Π strategy, geometric limitation, integro - geometric limitation.

Differensial o‘yinlar nazariyasida chegaralanishlar uchun Π strategiya muhim ahamiyatga ega. Har bir chegaralanish uchun alohida Π strategiyalar mavjud. Quyida ularni har birini ko‘rib chiqamiz.

Fazoda P va E obyekt harakatlanyapti

$$P: \begin{cases} \dot{x} = U \\ x(0) = x_0 \end{cases}$$

(1)

$$E: \begin{cases} \dot{y} = V \\ y(0) = y_0 \end{cases}$$

(2)

1. Geometrik chegaralanish :

$$a) |U| \leq \alpha ; |V| \leq \beta ; |U| = \sqrt{U_1^2 + \dots + U_n^2} ; |V| = \sqrt{V_1^2 + \dots + V_n^2}$$

$$b) U = (U_1; U_2) \rightarrow |U_1| \leq \alpha_1 , |U_2| \leq \alpha_2$$

$$V = (V_1; V_2) \rightarrow |V_1| \leq \beta_1 , |V_2| \leq \beta_2$$

Π strategiya : $U(v) = v - \lambda_G(v)\xi_0$, $\xi_0 = \frac{x_0 - y_0}{|x_0 - y_0|}$ bu yerda

$$\lambda_G(v) = \langle v, \xi_0 \rangle + \sqrt{\langle v, \xi_0 \rangle^2 + \alpha^2 - |v|^2}$$

$\alpha > \beta$ da tutish masalasi yechiladi ; $\alpha \leq \beta$ da qochish masalasi yechiladi .

2. Integro – geometrik chegaralanishli xol :

$$a) \int_0^\infty |U(s)|^2 ds \leq \rho_0, \quad (3)$$

$$|v| \leq \beta \quad (4)$$

$$b) \int_0^t |U_1(s)|^2 ds \leq \rho_{10}, \int_0^t |U_2(s)|^2 ds \leq \rho_{20}$$

$$|v_1| \leq \beta_1, \quad |v_2| \leq \beta_2$$

$$P: \dot{x} = U(t) x(0) = x_0 \rightarrow x(t) = x_0 + \int_0^t U(s) ds$$

$$E: \dot{y} = V(t) y(0) = y_0 \rightarrow y(t) = y_0 + \int_0^t V(s) ds$$

$$\text{Tutish masalasi: } \forall t^* : x(t^*) = y(t^*) \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Qochish masalasi: } x(t) \neq y(t), t \geq 0 \quad (6)$$

$$z + Tu = Tv, Tu = Tv - z, u = v - \frac{z}{T} \quad (7)$$

$$\int_0^T |U|^2 ds = \rho, T|U|^2 = \rho, |U|^2 = \frac{\rho}{T} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Quyidagicha belgilash kiritib olamiz: } \frac{|z|}{T} = \lambda \Rightarrow U = v - \lambda \xi, |U|^2 = \lambda \frac{\rho}{|z|}$$

$$\begin{cases} |U|^2 = |v|^2 - 2\lambda \langle v, \xi \rangle + \lambda^2 \\ \lambda \frac{\rho}{|z|} = |v|^2 - 2\lambda \langle v, \xi \rangle + \lambda^2 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \lambda^2 - 2\lambda \left(\frac{\rho}{2|z|} + \langle v, \xi \rangle \right) + v^2 = 0$$

$$(9)$$

$$\lambda_{1,2} = \frac{\rho}{2|z|} + \langle v, \xi \rangle \pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{\rho}{2|z|} + \langle v, \xi \rangle \right)^2 - |v|^2}$$

$$(10)$$

λ_1 va λ_2 ham musbat . Savol tuo‘iladi qaysi λ ni olamiz ?

$\lambda_1, \lambda_2 > 0$ agar , $\frac{\rho}{2|z|} + \langle v, \xi \rangle > 0$ bo‘lsa yechim mavjud bo‘lishi uchun ildiz osti

aniqlangan bo‘lishi kerak ya’ni $D = \left\{ (\rho, z, v) : \left(\frac{\rho}{2|z|} + \langle v, \xi \rangle \right)^2 - |v|^2 \geq 0 \right\}$

Integro – geometrik holda quvlovchini parallel yaqinlashtirish orqali (ω_1, ω_2) oraliqda tutish mumkin bo‘lar ekan . Biz bitta quvlovchi bitta qochuvchi bo‘lgan holda ko‘ramiz ya’ni λ_+ ni olamiz . Shuning uchun (10) ga yechim sifatida λ_1 ni tanlaymiz . Natijada hal qiluvchi funksiya deb,

$$\lambda(\rho, z, v) = \frac{\rho}{2|z|} + \langle v, \xi \rangle + \sqrt{\left(\frac{\rho}{2|z|} + \langle v, \xi \rangle \right)^2 - |v|^2} \quad (11)$$

funksiyani olamiz . n o‘lchovli fazoda $2n + 1$ ta yechimi bor. (11)- funksiyan

aniqlanish sohasini tahlil qilamiz $D = \left\{ (\rho, z, v) : \left(\frac{\rho}{2|z|} + \langle v, \xi \rangle \right)^2 - |v|^2 \geq 0 \right\}$

$$\left(\frac{\rho}{2|z|} + \langle v, \xi \rangle + |v| \right) \left(\frac{\rho}{2|z|} + \langle v, \xi \rangle - |v| \right) \geq 0 \text{ demak ,}$$

$$\frac{\rho}{2|z|} + \langle v, \xi \rangle - |v| \geq 0 \quad (12)$$

bo‘lishi kerak . (12) tengsizlikning geometrik mohiyati (v ga nisbatan):

$$a^2 = \frac{\rho}{2|z|} , a^2 + v_1 \xi_1 + \dots + v_n \xi_n - \sqrt{v_1^2 + \dots + v_n^2} \geq 0 \text{ figura hosil bo‘ladi .}$$

Soddalashtirish uchun tekislikda ko‘raylik . $a^2 + v_1 \xi_1 + v_2 \xi_2 - \sqrt{v_1^2 + v_2^2} \geq 0$

$$\xi_0 = \frac{x_0 - y_0}{|x_0 - y_0|}, x_0 = (0;0), y_0 = (1;0); \xi_0 (-1;0), \xi_1 = -1, \xi_2 = 0$$

$$a^2 - v_1 - \sqrt{v_1^2 + v_2^2} \geq 0 , a^2 \geq v_1 + \sqrt{v_1^2 + v_2^2} \geq 0 , a=1 \text{ desak , } v_1 + \sqrt{v_1^2 + v_2^2} \leq 1,$$

$$\sqrt{v_1^2 + v_2^2} \leq 1 - v_1$$

$$1 - 2v_1 + v_1^2 \geq v_1^2 + v_2^2, 1 - 2v_1 \geq v_2^2, v_1 \leq \frac{1 - v_2^2}{2}$$

D sohamiz parabolaning ichi ekan . Uch o‘lchovli fazoda ko‘rsak , paraboloid bo‘lib qolar ekan . Agar $a \neq 1$ bo‘lsa uchi $\frac{a}{2}$ da bo‘lar ekan tekislikda .

$$\xi_0(-1, 0, 0); a^2 - v_1 - \sqrt{v_1^2 + v_2^2 + v_3^2} \geq 0, a^2 - v_1 \geq \sqrt{v_1^2 + v_2^2 + v_3^2}$$

$$a^4 - 2a^2v_1 + v_1^2 \geq v_1^2 + v_2^2 + v_3^2, a^4 - 2a^2v_1 \geq v_2^2 + v_3^2, v_1 \leq \frac{a^4}{2a^2} - \frac{v_2^2 + v_3^2}{2a^2}, v_1 \leq \frac{a^2}{2} - \frac{v_2^2 + v_3^2}{2a^2}$$

$$\beta \leq \frac{a^2}{2} = \frac{\rho}{4|z|} \Rightarrow \rho \geq 4\beta|z|. \text{ Demak , xulosa (11) } \lambda(\rho, z, v) \text{ funksiya } \rho \geq 4\beta|z|$$

bo‘lganda $\forall |v| \leq \beta$ uchun aniqlangan .

$$(11) \text{ ko‘rinishni yuqoridagi } U = v - \lambda\xi, |U|^2 = \lambda \frac{\rho}{|z|} \text{ tenglikka olib kelib}$$

qo‘yamiz va quyidagi strategiyani hosil qilamiz :

$$\begin{cases} U(\rho, z, v) = v - \lambda(\rho, z, v)\xi \\ |U(\rho, z, v)|^2 = \lambda(\rho, z, v) \frac{\rho}{|z|} \end{cases}$$

(13)

(1) va (2) tenglamadan quyidagi tenglamani hosil qilamiz

$$\begin{cases} \dot{z} = U - v \\ z(0) = z_0 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

bu yerda $z = x - y, \dot{x} = U; z_0 = x_0 - y_0, \dot{y} = v; \dot{x} - \dot{y} = U - v$

(14) ko‘rinishdagi U ni o‘rniga (13) ni 1-qatorini qo‘yamiz natijada :

$$\begin{cases} \dot{z} = -\lambda(\rho, z, v)\xi \\ z(0) = z_0 \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

$$\rho(t) = \rho_0 - \int_0^t |U(s)|^2 ds$$

(16)

(16) tenglamaga $|U|^2$ ni o‘rniga (13) ni 2-qatorini qo‘yamiz

$$\rho(t) = \rho_0 - \int_0^t \lambda(\rho(s), z(s), v(s)) \frac{\rho(s)}{|z(s)|} ds$$
 tenglikni hosil qilamiz . Endi har ikki

tomondan hosila olaylik

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\rho}(t) = -\lambda(\rho, z, v) \frac{\rho}{|z|} \\ \rho(0) = \rho_0 \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

(15) va (17) lardan quyidagi natijaga ega bo‘lamiz

$$\begin{cases} \dot{z} = -\lambda(\rho(t), z(t), v(t)) \frac{z(t)}{|z(t)|} \\ \dot{\rho} = -\lambda(\rho(t), z(t), v(t)) \frac{\rho(t)}{|z(t)|} \\ z(0) = z_0, \rho(0) = \rho_0 \end{cases}$$

(18)

(18) dan (ρ, z) ga nisbatan differensial tenglamalar sistemasi hosil bo‘lishi kelib chiqdi.

(18) sistema noxiziqli differensial sistema . Agar $z \neq 0$ bo‘lsa bu sistemaning o‘ng tomonidagi funksiya $\rho \geq 4\beta|z|$ shartda uzluksiz ((ρ, z) ga nisbatan) . Funksiya t ga nisbatan esa o‘lchovli funksiya (ya’ni Karatedore shartlari bajarilyapti) deyiladi. Karatedore sharti bo‘lishi uchun , Karatedore tenglamasining o‘ng tomoni z bo‘yicha Lipshist shartini qanoatlantirishi kerak ya’ni

$$|f(z_1, t) - f(z_2, t)| \leq L |z_1 - z_2| \quad (19)$$

(18) tenglamaning o‘ng tomonidagi funksiyalar (ρ, z) bo‘yicha $z \neq 0$ holda Karatedore shartlari o‘rinli . Shuning uchun (18) sistemani yagona yechimi mavjud bo‘ladi . (18) tenglamadan quyidagicha almashtirish hosil qilamiz

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \dot{z}_1 = -\lambda(\rho(t), z(t), v(t)) \frac{z_1(t)}{|z(t)|} \\ \dot{z}_2 = -\lambda(\rho(t), z(t), v(t)) \frac{z_2(t)}{|z(t)|} \\ \dots \\ \dot{z}_n = -\lambda(\rho(t), z(t), v(t)) \frac{z_n(t)}{|z(t)|} \end{array} \right. \Rightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\dot{z}_1}{z_1} = -\lambda(\rho(t), z(t), v(t)) \frac{1}{|z(t)|} \\ \frac{\dot{z}_2}{z_2} = -\lambda(\rho(t), z(t), v(t)) \frac{1}{|z(t)|} \\ \dots \\ \frac{\dot{z}_n}{z_n} = -\lambda(\rho(t), z(t), v(t)) \frac{1}{|z(t)|} \end{array} \right.$$

endi integrallasak ,

$$\ln z_i \Big|_0^t = -\int_0^t \lambda(\rho(t), z(t), v(t)) \frac{1}{|z(t)|} ds; z_i(t) = z_i(0) e^{-\int_0^t \lambda(\rho(t), z(t), v(t)) \frac{1}{|z(t)|} ds}, i = \overline{1, n}$$

$$e^{-\int_0^t \lambda(\rho(t), z(t), v(t)) \frac{1}{|z(t)|} ds} = h(t) \text{ deb olsak ,}$$

$$z(t) = z_0 h(t)$$

(20)

hosil bo‘ladi . Xuddi shu kabi ,

$$\begin{cases} \rho(t) = \rho_0 h(t) \\ z(t) = z_0 h(t) \end{cases}$$

(21)

bu yerda $h(t) = h(z, \rho, v, t)$. (21) ni (11) ga olib borib qo‘yaylik

$$\lambda(\rho, z, v) = \frac{\rho}{2|z|} + \langle v, \xi \rangle + \sqrt{\left(\frac{\rho}{2|z|} + \langle v, \xi \rangle\right)^2 - |v|^2} = \frac{\rho_0 h}{2|z_0| h} + \left\langle v, \frac{z_0 h}{|z_0| h} \right\rangle + \sqrt{\left(\frac{\rho}{2|z|} + \langle v, \xi \rangle\right)^2 - |v|^2} = \lambda(\rho_0, z_0, v)$$

Demak, boshlano‘ich holatdagi (ρ_0, z_0) ni bilsak bo‘ldi ekan.

Ta‘rif: Integro –geometrik differensial o‘yinda Π strategiya deb, quyidagi funksiyaga aytamiz

$$U(v) = v - \lambda_{IG}(v) \xi_0 \quad (22)$$

bu yerda
$$\lambda_{IG}(v) = \frac{\rho_0}{2|z_0|} + \langle v, \xi_0 \rangle + \sqrt{\left(\frac{\rho_0}{2|z_0|} + \langle v, \xi_0 \rangle\right)^2 - |v|^2}$$

Mavzu bo‘yicha tarixiy ma‘lumot: Strategiyalar quvish masalasi qadimdan olimlarni qiziqtirgan. Eramizdan 2000 yil avval Xitoy qo‘lyozmalarida “Burgut va O‘lja masalasi” o‘rganilgan bunda burgut o‘z o‘ljasini izma –iz quvish strategiyasi orqali harakatlanib ushlab qolish masalasi ko‘rilgan. Lekin matematika rivoji u davrda bu masalani yechishga yetarli bo‘lmagan. 1732- yil fransuz gidrografi va matematigi Bagauer “Tulki va Quyon” masalasini yechadi. Bunda quyin ma‘lim to‘o‘ri chiziq bo‘yicha qochib borganda tulki uni izma –iz quvish natijasida qaysi trayektoriya orqali harakat qilishi mumkinligi m α asaasi yechildi. Bu masala amerikalik olim Lokning “Zambaraklarni boshqarish” kitobida bafurcha tahlil qilinib yechimlari keltirilgan.

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